

Conference Abstract

Study of the normal blood picture of *Ceratitis capitata* Wiedemann, 1824 (Insecta: Diptera, Tephritidae) larvae and after infection with entomopathogenic nematodes

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Abstract

The Mediterranean fruit fly, *Ceratitis capitata*, Wiedemann (Diptera: Tephritidae), is one of the world's most destructive fruit pests. At least four time transient populations of the species were established during vegetation season in Bulgaria.

The insects have very effective defense system against different pathogens, parasites and alien substances. The cellular immune response is realized by some types of circulating hemocytes. Entomopathogenic nematodes (EPNs) have their own symbiotic bacteria in their intestine. When they enter insect hosts the released bacteria depress insect immune capacity and protect nematodes and bacteria from cellular and humoral host reaction.

The aim of present study is to evaluate immune response of medfly to infestation of a local population of *Steinernema arenarium* (Artyukhovsky) on the base of differential hemocyte counts (DHC).

Laboratory population of *Ceratitis capitata* (originated from Thessaloniki, North Greece) was cultivated at 24°C, 65-70% humidity and 16/8 h Day/Night in growing chamber. Synchronized prepupae reared on artificial diet were used for the experiments. Entomopathogenic nematodes of species *Steinernema arenarium* were from a laboratory culture originated from Zemen Gorge. Infestation with about 200 iJ per tube was made. Twenty fly specimens per variant and per control were processed in each variant. Samples of hemolymph were taken by cutting the end of prepupa abdomen at 8th, 24th and 36th h after infestation. Hemolymph of 5 specimens was stained by Gimza's method on a slide. The hemocyte identification was based on morphology under microscope Olympus BX51. Changes in host immune answer were accessed by differential hemocyte counts (DHC) (10 counts of 150 per slide) of parasitized and healthy specimens. Treatment means and variances were analyzed by Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA and Tukey HSD test by pairs.

Six well-defined haemocyte types were distinguished in the haemolymph of infected and uninfected *C. capitata* larvae: prohemocytes (PR), plasmacytes (PL), granulocytes (GR), spherulocytes (SP), oenocytoids (OE) and podocytes (PO). On the 8th h there were no significant differences in hemotypes between infested or healthy specimens. Prohemocytes, spherulocytes, podocytes and oenocytoids are rare about 1-3%, plasmacytes are about 30-40% and granulocytes are the most abundant group – 58-61%. Similar proportions are observed in the non infested specimens on the 24th hour. Relative part of podocytes in the infested specimens on the 24th h was significantly higher than in all other variants. On the 36th h no hemolymph was available in infested larvae and the control specimens formed pupa stage at 20°C.

Keywords

Mediterranean fruit fly, hemocytes

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.